

The development of comparative linguistics in the sphere of ESP teaching

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Abstract:

The article discusses the features of terminological differentiation of two disciplines as part of comparative linguistics, teaching related oriental languages in ESP directions (compare historical linguistics) and for terminological marking of the second in this direction, the term "comparative synchronic linguistics" is introduced.

Keywords: comparative method, comparative linguistics, terminology, comparative-historical, comparative synchronic, related languages, compares historical linguistics.

The birth and functioning of the comparative-historical method became the basis for the formation of a new independent linguistic discipline- as - comparative historical linguistics, which is based on the work Fr.Bopp, R.Rusk, J.Grimm, A.H.Vostokov, written in the first quarter XIX century. [see: 1; 2. C. 6 and others]. Comparison method and comparative historical language knowledge contributed to the formation of other linguistic disciplines, languages based on comparison [see: 1- 8; and etc.].¹ Thus, the development of comparative historical linguistics became the basis for the formation of linguistic disciplines such as linguistic typology, comparative typology, and comparative linguistics. All these linguistic

disciplines are based on the use of a comparison method that, on the one hand, it unites them into one big whole - into a comparative language knowledge, and on the other hand, differentiate them into different linguistic disciplines [see: 1-3; nine; and etc.]. Comparative-historical linguistics explores the diachronic aspect related languages, identifying in them general concepts, categories, elements, proving the commonness, kinship of the common origin of the studied languages. For example, the study of the law of synchronism of the Turkic languages in diachronic from the general aspect shows that in all the Turkic languages two types of synchronicity: lingual synchronicity and labial synchronicity, which functioned simultaneously (in aggregate) and in the sound speech stream merged into one whole. 1 Рец. проф. Сапарова К.О. (УзГУМЯ, Ташкент); проф. У.М. Бахтикиреева (РУДН). "Science and Education" Scientific Journal June 2021 / Volume 2 Special Issue 2 www.openscience.uz 7 R.K.Rusk: establishing grammatical and phonetic correspondences, chronologization layers of vocabulary. J.Grimm: three stages of development of the human language, an appeal to sound changes, the law of the first movement of consonants in Germanic languages (the law Grima). A.Kh.Vostokov: "first-class" and "second-class" words, periodization of the Slavic language. Comparative-historical linguistics in the middle of the nineteenth century. Comparative Historical Issues linguistics in the works of young grammarians. The problem of changing the meanings of words in the interpretation of G.Paul. Psychological direction. Comparative historical problems in the works of F.F.Fortunatov. Questions and Answers comparative historical linguistics and the typology of languages in the works of representatives Kazan linguistic school. Morris Swadesh (1909-1967) glottochronology method for measuring speed language changes (most often referring to lexicostatistics, i.e.

comparing lists of 100 or 200 words of the compared languages from the most stable part of the vocabulary

Methods for learning and describing languages, especially in different oriental languages scientific knowledge as a process, general scientific research methods and their application in linguistics are considered to be the main one. Linguistic modeling and comparative method are very vital in analyzing the history of foreign languages , like Chinese, Japanese, Urdu, Hindi, Dari and others. Comparative study of related and unrelated languages: implicit juxtaposition and language parallels.

Typological method as well as Quantitative methods for defining typological language options are very important one in the history of language teaching. Types of contrastive analysis ("pure" and complex analysis, vertical and horizontal analysis, one-sided and two-sided analysis). "Error analysis": theory and practice. Frequency dictionaries and their use in matching. Statistical methodology for learning language and text. Logical-mathematical modeling of language processes. Fuzzy logic. Descriptive methods: private techniques and techniques. Highlighting units. Distributive analysis, distribution models, component analysis, methods for determining semantic factors, and also determination of the semantic valence of linguistic units have their own position in the history and theory of foreign language teaching methods. Nevertheless, we decided to use the term typology, since, in comparative typology, they are equally investigated as related, and unrelated languages. If we use the term (qiyosiy) typology (literally: comparative typology), then we "run into" the meaning in which the comparison of related languages is initially laid down, i.e. a comparative the typology of related languages, while the boundaries of the comparative typology logic are broader: it

studies languages, regardless of their relationship, especially whenever we learn or teach any kind of oriental languages or foreign languages we often use the comparative methods of teaching. However not only the methods are considered the essential one, but also the foreign teacher's contribution is also the main resource in teaching sphere. here is meant that most of the native speakers of foreign countries tent to be more energetic and are respected more curiously by language learners. Furthermore, it is considered to be more effective way of learning and teaching by both side of the learners in ESP directions, therefore comparative linguistics always need to exchange the experience pf foreign teachers in our country and need to lead their experience in our teaching specialties.

References

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